
Information Communication Technology (ICT) and Libraries

Dr. Ekta Menkudale

Librarian

Shivramji Moghe Arts, Commerce and Science College

Kelapur (Pandharkawada) Dist. Yavatmal

Corresponding Author – Dr. Ekta Menkudale

DOI - 10.5281/zenodo.15254553

Abstract:

Information is very essential for every human being as per their need. The information is transferred from one generation to another by acquired, store, process, evaluate, retrieve and disseminate with using various sources like; books, journals and manuscripts. Due to invention of ICT and its application in library, the source of information has changed from physical information resources to the digital/electronic information resources. Currently ICT has played vital role in producing, accessing, processing, storing, retrieving and disseminating information in every field of all sectors. All the modern libraries are used ICT for library automation and digitization of books and other reading material. While using ICT in library, the library system goes to paperless library, library without boundaries, virtual library etc. Due to impact of ICT all the modern libraries are changed their shapes from store house of books to the power house of knowledge. The modern libraries are not restricted to store the physical books and journals but subscribes e-books, e-journals, e-databases and the libraries are known as hybrid library..

Keywords: *User Interface, Student Widgets, Expected Results*

Introduction:

A library is a collection of books and non-book materials stored and organised for use. A library plays a vital role in every educational institutions from primary level to the higher education. The modern educational institution libraries not only store printed reading material like; books, periodicals and newspapers but also subscribe to e-books, ejournals, CDs/DVDs and purchase educational databases. The main reason of e-collection in modern libraries is to equip with information and communication technology. A library, whether public, national, academic, research or special library has its main objective and function to collect, organise and disseminate information to its end users efficiently and effectively. The libraries of the 21st century have to conceive not merely as a store house of books and others reading materials, but

also be an effective mechanism to facilitate and dissemination of knowledge, promoting information and knowledge sharing. The libraries of the 21st century should transmit today's literate society to a knowledge-based society of tomorrow. A library is a fulcrum or support for the entire range of academic activities on an education institution. The recommendations of Educational Testing Services refers to the Information Technology (IT) was used before many years, specifically in the United States, and it also refers to the electronic accessing, processing and storage of required information, but not for the transmission of information. However, ICT represents the group of activities and technologies that covers into the group of Information Technology and Communication Technologies. World Industry, International Medias and academics has increasingly

currently used IT to describe this group of ICTs. The actual benefits of adding “communication” doesn’t derive from including specific technologies, such as routers or servers, but from the dynamism implicit in interconnected social, economic, and information networks..

Objectives of the research:

1. To study the importance of information and communication technology in library work
2. To study the benefits of information and communication technology to the library
3. To study the disadvantages of information and communication technology to the library

Importance of Information Communication Technology (ITC) in Library Work:

Books are the basic foundation of a library and are an important factor in the personal, social, political, educational and economic development of human life. Just as a human needs food to meet the energy needs of the body, he needs books to meet the need for knowledge or information. This need is fulfilled through the library. Today's man has become technophile. Computers, Internet and smart mobiles have revolutionized human life. Now most of the knowledge needs of man are being met through mobiles and computers. Since ancient times, the knowledge needs of man were met through libraries, now this place has been taken by e-books in books. Through information communication technology, one can get the required book online from any corner of the world. Humans have now started finding digital media more convenient than physical libraries. Due to this, the importance of digital libraries in human life has increased. Digital library allows it to get more world-class information in less time and does not require much space to store this information

and the work can be completed quickly and most importantly, one e-book can be read at the same time. But readers can read through different computers. Freely and any new service related to that book or new books, magazines, any new information is also easily available. Digital library is a type of library. Through this, users can easily read every type of book sitting at home through the internet. The data in this library is stored in digital format (as opposed to printed, microform or other media) and can be accessed through computers. The content can be stored locally or accessed remotely. Nowadays, India is also rapidly becoming a Digital India. Day by day, the Government of India has brought the facility of Digital Library to India through new apps for the people and the Government of India has given special encouragement to Digital Library in the new educational policy. In a digital library, soft copies of documents are saved on CDs in PDF format. Through this, magazines, newspapers, articles, books, images, sound files and videos can be easily viewed on the internet. For this, there is no need to call any expert, we can easily access it ourselves. These digital files can also be printed. Digital libraries are also called electronic libraries, virtual libraries, hybrid libraries. A digital library, unlike other forms of media such as print or microform, is a special form of library that includes digital assets. Such digital assets can be in the form of visual materials, text, audio or video electronic media as it is a library. It also has features to manage, store and retrieve the media or files that make up the archive. The content in a digital library can be stored locally or can be accessed through a network if stored remotely.

Studying the benefits of information communication technology to libraries:

1. Information communication technology allows the reader to access any information or books from around the

world through the Internet, sitting at home on his computer or mobile. For this, he does not need to go anywhere.

2. Information communication technology allows the reader to access the information he needs at any time, 24 hours a day and 365 days a year, through digital libraries.
3. Digital libraries allow him to access richer content in a more structured way. He does not need to search. Today, Google Baba provides you with instant information.
4. An exact copy of the original can be made at any time without any deterioration in the quality of the book.
5. A specific digital library can easily link to any other source in other digital libraries.
6. Traditional libraries are limited by the storage space of the book. There is a lot of information in digital libraries. Storage capacity: Because digital information requires very little physical space. Due to this, we can include lakhs of books in a small hard disk.
7. The cost of maintaining a digital library is much less than that of a traditional library. A traditional library has to spend a lot of money on staff, maintenance of books, rent and additional books. A digital library does not require such a huge cost.
8. Digital libraries can be made available in rural/remote areas in every corner of the world.
9. With the increase in information resources on CD/DVD for storing books in digital form; their cost and maintenance are much less than paper books.
10. Digital libraries save paper and protect the environment.

Studying the disadvantages of information communication technology in libraries:

1. **Violation of author's copyright:**
Digitization of books made available through information communication

technology violates copyright law because the work of one author can be freely transferred by another without his permission. Therefore, digital libraries make it difficult to prevent the illegal distribution of information created by the author.

2. **Cost of information communication technology system is high:** The cost of the necessary infrastructure for creating a digital library created through information communication technology is usually very high, so it is beyond the ability of the common man to use it.
3. **Efficiency:** Due to the abundance of digital information, it becomes difficult to find the right material for a particular task.
4. **Access speed:** As more and more computers are connected to the Internet. Its access speed decreases. If new technologies are not developed to solve the problem, the Internet will be full of error messages in the near future.
5. **Bandwidth:** High bandwidth is required for high quality information transmission. But due to its overuse, the bandwidth capacity is decreasing. Due to which the right information is not available.
6. **Environment:** Digital libraries cannot reproduce the environment of a traditional library. Many people also find it easier to read printed materials than reading materials on a computer screen. The reader can make it available as a reference for his future reference. This concession is not available in digital libraries. Therefore, readers are reluctant to use digital libraries.

Conclusion:

Today's man has become technology-loving and is using technology more and more in his daily life. Information and communication technology, computers and digital libraries are fulfilling the

knowledge needs of man in today's era. Keeping in mind the changing needs of man in the present era, it has become necessary for the library to be technology-friendly. Considering the changes taking place in the educational sector at the university, national and international levels, the curriculum and the process of studying are constantly changing over time. Similarly, the process of taking exams is constantly changing. Now competitive exams are also being held online. Therefore, it is necessary to change the process of storing libraries and books over time. Among them, it has become necessary to create digital libraries and adopt information and communication technology to reach the doors of the readers. Everything has its advantages and disadvantages, so its importance does not decrease. For this, using technology in libraries to make their course materials and services user-oriented is the need of the hour and digital libraries are one of its mediums. This unit describes the concept of library, important components of a library, benefits of a library and future of a library etc. Now you need to increase the use of various types of libraries, their functions and services, computer applications, specific library operations. In order to provide efficient and timely services to the users, there is an urgent need to computerize libraries. Moreover, in this busy world, every moment of the users is valuable. It is essential for a service-oriented organization

that it is the responsibility of the library to try to save the time of its users. For these reasons, it is necessary to digitize the library to provide book services to the rural areas of India through digital libraries with emphasis on computerized management.

References:

1. Gupta S.R. Chardhury: Poonam & Verma, Journal of Library & Information Science
2. Ranganathan, S.R. (1963). Five Laws of Library Science, Bomba, Asia.
3. Ranganathan, S.R. (1966). Teaching Library Science with Slant to Documentation.
4. Zala, Lavji N. Patel, Niraj R : LIBRARY PORTAL : A GATEWAY OF INFORMATION-Inflibnet
5. Brijwasi, H. (23rd Sep 2016).Library Portal of Smt. Sharadchandrika Suresh Patil College of Pharmacy: A Study. Innovative Application of Technology in Libraries .
6. Jamali, Hamid R. Google and the scholar : the role of Google in scientists' informationseeking behavior, Online Information Review.
7. Zala, Lavji N. Patel, Niraj R: LIBRARY PORTAL : A GATEWAY OF INFORMATION - Inflibnet
8. Newspaper articles and articles on the websiteWebsites & Newspaper Articals